

ROMANTICISM IS AN ESSENTIAL PART OF ENGLISH LITERATURE

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Abstract. *Romanticism focused on emotions and the inner life of the humankind and inseparable part of the world literature. In Romantic theory, art was valuable not so much as a mirror of the external world, but as a source of illumination of the world within. This research has defined the ideas about Romanticism. By investing this paper I try to identify the notion of Romanticism in literature. This article also shows the works of writers in English Literature. To reveal this work we broadly approach to the works of most famous figures in the history of literature. Romantic writers have created their own works in the movement of Romantic period.*

The Romantics asserted the importance of the individual, the unique, even the eccentric.

This research paper has also examined the motives and opinions about Romanticism. By closely researching a few works of writings in the period of Romanticism the research confirms this action played a crucial role in the developing of world literature.

Key role: *English literature, Romanticism, Romantic writers, Romantic periods, English, England, literary criticism.*

Introduction. English literature is a component part of the world literature. Its best national traditions have played an important role in enriching and development of the world literature. English literature consists of poetry, prose and drama written in the English language by authors in England, Scotland, and Wales. These lands have produced many outstanding writers. English literature is a rich literature. It includes masterpieces in many forms, particularly a novel; a short story, an epic and lyric poetry, an essay, literary criticism, and drama. English literature is also one of the oldest national literatures in the world.

Main body. The Romantic movement, which has originated in Germany but rapidly spread to other European countries such as; England, France. It reached to America around the year 1820, some twenty years after William Wordsworth and Samuel Taylor Coleridge had revolutionized English poetry by publishing *Lyrical Ballads*. In America as in Europe, fresh new vision excited artistic and intellectual circles. Yet there was a difference: Romanticism in America coincided with the period of national expansion and the discovery of a distinctive American voice. The solidification of a national identity and the surging idealism and passion of Romanticism nurtured the masterpieces of “the American Renaissance.”

Romantic ideas centered around art as inspiration, the spiritual and aesthetic dimension of nature, and metaphors of organic growth. Art, rather than science, Romantics argued, could best express universal truth. The Romantics underscored the importance of expressive art for the individual and society. In his essay “The Poet” (1844), Ralph Waldo Emerson, perhaps the most influential writer of the Romantic era, asserts:¹ In England, Romanticism had its greatest influence from the end of the eighteenth century up to 1832, all the way up to about 1870. Its primary vehicle of expression was in poetry.

¹ Reynolds, Nicole. 2010. *Building Romanticism: Literature and Architecture in Nineteenth-century Britain*. University of Michigan Press

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For all men live by truth, and stand in need of expression. In love, in art, in avarice, in politics, in labor, in games, we study to utter our painful secret. The man is only half himself, the other half is his expression.

The development of the self became a major theme; self-awareness a primary method. If, according to Romantic theory, self and nature were one, self-awareness was not a selfish dead end but a mode of knowledge opening up the universe. If one's self were one with all humanity, then the individual had a moral duty to reform social inequalities and relieve human suffering.²

The Romantic Period in English literature is taken to begin with the publication of Wordsworth and Coleridge's Lyrical Ballads and end with the death of the novelist, Sir Walter Scott. The historical and literary contexts effects covered a broader time span.

No other period in English literature displays more variety in style, theme, and content than the Romantic Movement of the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries. Furthermore, no period has been the topic of so much disagreement and confusion over its defining principles and aesthetics.

The dates of the Romantic period of literature are not precise and the term 'romantic' was itself not widely used until after the period in question. Conventionally, the period begins in 1798, which saw the publication by Wordsworth and Coleridge of their Lyrical Ballads, and ends in 1832, a year which saw the death of Sir Walter Scott and the enactment by Parliament of the First Reform Bill. These years link literary and political events. The Romantic period was an era in which a literary revolution took place alongside social and economic revolutions. In some histories of literature the Romantic period is called the 'Age of Revolutions'.³

In terms of literary history, the publication of Lyrical Ballads in 1798 is seen as a landmark. The volume contains many of the best-known Romantic poems. The second edition in 1800 contained a Preface in which Wordsworth discusses the theories of poetry which were to be so influential on many of his and Coleridge's contemporaries. The Preface represents a poetic manifesto which is very much in the spirit of the age. The movement towards greater freedom and democracy in political and social affairs is paralleled by poetry which sought to overturn the existing regime and establish a new, more 'democratic' poetic order. To do this, the writers used 'the real language of men' (Preface to Lyrical Ballads) and even, in the case of Byron and Shelley, got directly involved in political activities themselves.

Conclusion. The Romantic age in literature is often contrasted with the Classical or Augustan age which preceded it. The comparison is valuable, for it is not simply two different attitudes to literature which are being compared but two different ways of seeing and experiencing life. The Romantics developed ways of writing which tried to capture the ebb and flow of individual experience in forms and language which were intended to be closer to everyday speech and more accessible to the general reader.⁴ Romanticism is celebrated as the primitive and elevated "regular people" as deserving of celebration, which was an innovation at the time.

Romanticism is also fixated on nature as a primordial force and encouraged the concept of loneliness as necessary for spiritual and artistic development.

² ROMANTIC PERIOD IN ENGLISH LITERATURE. (1796-1832)

³ The Routledge History of Literature in English. Britain and Ireland. Third edition. Ronald Carter and John Mcrae.

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